

The high yield of IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R was attributed to a high number of panicles. It showed midparent heterosis for all characters at both sites.

Results indicate that hybrids developed specifically for irrigated lowland can be grown under rainfed conditions and still exhibit heterosis

even when subjected to water deficit. Results further suggest that hybrid rices can be developed for rainfed environments. □

Grain quality and nutritional value

Modified method for apparent amylose content (AC) of milled rice

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Colorimetric amylose assay based on amylose standard alone overestimates AC of milled rice because of amylopectin-iodine complex interference at acid pH. Addition of amylopectin (waxy rice starch, 0.6% amylose) to amylose in the standard mixture lowers amylose values, particularly for high-amylose rice. These values are probably closer to true AC since the potato amylose standard is only 80% pure.

Amylose values, however, are expressed on milled rice basis of about 90% starch. Recently, starches of high-amylose indica rices were shown to have the same true AC (about 18%) as low-amylose japonica rices. The increased iodine-blue color was due mainly to

Apparent AC of defatted milled rice flour in pH 4.5-4.8 acetate buffer based on amylose standard and amylose-amylopectin standard with starch content calculated to 90% and 70% of milled rice. IRRRI, 1988.

Variety name	Apparent AC (%) based on		
	Amylose alone	Amylose + amylopectin to	
		90% starch	70% starch
IR29	8.2	0.6	1.9
IR2071-137-5	16.2	9.2	10.6
IR24	19.9	13.2	14.6
IR64	28.2	22.0	23.4
IR8	32.2	26.2	27.6
Mean	20.9	14.2	15.6

*Standard: amylose 0-30 mg/100 ml; amylose: amylopectin 0-30: 90-60 mg/100 ml for 90% starch or 0-30: 90-40 mg/100 ml for 70% starch with defatted milled rice standards at 100 mg/100 ml.

high-iodine binding amylopectin; thus, apparent AC of high-amylose rice starches is 25-26%. High-amylose rice amylopectin has iodine complexing properties different from waxy rice amylopectin, while waxy and low-amylose rice amylopectins are similar in branching properties.

Because classification of milled rice AC into low (10-20%), intermediate (20-25%), and high (>25%) is well accepted and documented, we propose maintaining such classification but calling it apparent AC.

These values can be obtained for defatted rice flour in the amylose-amylopectin standard method by

adjusting starch level (amylose + amylopectin) from 90% to 70% of the milled rice weight. Adding a constant correction factor, 1.4%, to all amylose values based on the 90% starch standard maintains the above classification scheme (see table). With this method, calibration is at pH 4.5-4.8 in acetate buffer, reducing errors inherent in the Williams procedure at alkaline pH. Excess iodine characterizes the acid pH procedure as reflected in the greenish amylose-iodine solution. Defatting with refluxing 95% ethanol gives more accurate apparent amylose values than using undefatted samples, because fat contents of samples are not necessarily identical at similar milling conditions.

The detailed procedure is available upon request. □

Grain characteristics of traditional Basmati varieties of northwest India

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We collected 23 traditional Basmati varieties from northwest India and

studied their grain characteristics (see table).

We divided varieties into two groups. Varieties of group A—HBC-5 (Havana Basmati collection), HBC-85, Pakistani Basmati (Amritsar), Basmati Kota, and Karnal local—have a growth duration of 145-150 d, and are phenotypically similar to Karnal local, which fetches the highest prices in the domestic and export markets.

Grain characteristics of Basmati varieties, India.

Character	Group A (n = 5)			Group B (n = 18)		
	Range	Mean	SEM	Range	Mean	SEM
Milled rice length (mm)	1.00 - 7.35	1.20	0.062	6.17 - 6.87	6.51	0.041
Brown rice (% of rough rice)	78.20 - 79.40	78.74	0.235	78.60 - 80.50	79.80	0.128
Total milled rice (% of rough rice)	65.30 - 67.70	66.72	0.533	65.80 - 68.80	67.31	0.198
Head rice (% of rough rice)	32.20 - 42.50	38.14	1.873	25.10 - 58.50	47.24	1.846
Milled rice breadth (mm)	1.74 - 1.78	1.76	0.008	1.69 - 1.89	1.81	0.013
Length-to-breadth ratio	4.02 - 4.13	4.08	0.018	3.15 - 3.84	3.56	0.037
Length of cooked grain (mm)	13.90 - 15.00	14.55	0.198	12.20 - 14.00	13.26	0.127
Elongation ratio	1.89 - 2.12	2.02	0.042	1.89 - 2.19	2.04	0.021
Alkali spreading value	3.80 - 5.00	4.28	0.224	3.00 - 4.00	3.46	0.087
Amylose content (%)	21.00 - 23.00	22.00	0.316	21.00 - 23.50	21.86	0.212

Varieties of 135-140 d duration represent group B. HBC-30,40,45,46, 85,98 and 136; Mohabawali, Kanwali, Chanderbani 1 and 11, Niranjapur, and Ramgarh (named after the villages of Dehra-Dun Valley) are phenotypically similar to Basmati 370 whereas Hansraj and N-10B resemble Type-3. Among these cultures, only Basmati 370 and Type-3 have been officially released for

cultivation and seed production.

Major differences in groups A and B (see table) appear to be in growth duration, milled rice length, length-to-breadth ratio, head rice recovery, and alkali spreading value. Difference in head rice recovery could possibly be due to postharvest handling and mechanical factors, but the lower mean value

(38.14%) in group A as compared to group B (47.24%) suggests higher vulnerability of longer grains to breakage.

Farmers grow Basmati 370, Type-3, and Karnal local under different names, warranting study of key diagnostic characteristics to establish their identities.□

Disease resistance

Varietal ranking of blast (BI) severity in Korean farmers' fields

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Varietal reactions to rice BI in farmers' fields and their relative ranking help determine resistance level, virulence frequency, disease pressure, and their interactions. Such rankings can guide cultural management.

To develop a varietal ranking in Korea, we used an indirect method without taking a comprehensive disease survey. We compared 56 varieties released in Korea: 26 of Tongil type (Korean indica) and 30 of japonica type. Most of the 51 varieties released before 1984 were grown in a considerable area. Cultivation area and duration of varieties vary widely, often highly influenced by BI. Criteria for comparisons were the relative degree of maximum leaf or panicle BI incidence and severity, yield losses due to BI, and chemical requirement. Varieties were classified into 9 groups (Table 1), and common features of five odd-numbered ranking groups were described (Table 2). Ranking groups 2,4, 6, and 8 reflect severity levels between those of the odd-numbered groups described. To minimize subjectivity, five evaluators rated each variety several times until they unanimously agreed.

Varieties scored 1 or 2, such as Taebaeg and Cheongcheong, were

Table 1. Relative ranking of Korean varieties based on BI severity in farmers' field. Korea, 1988.

Rank	Tongil type	Japonica type
1	<u>Taebaeg (79)</u> , Chupung (79)	
2		
3	Cheongcheong (79), <u>Samgang (182)</u>	
4	Palgwang (78), Milyang 42 (78) Milyang 30 (77)	
5	Gaya (82), <u>Weonpung (83)</u> , <u>Baegyung (82)</u> , <u>Shinwang (82)</u>	Shinseonchd (82), <u>Seomjin (82)</u> , Nonglim Na 1 (67)
6	<u>Seogwang (79)</u> , <u>Hangangchal (79)</u>	Nongbaeg (69), <u>Odae (82)</u> , Seolag (79), <u>Sobaeg (82)</u> , Boggwang (81), Dobong (79), Sangpung (81), Kwanak (79), Yeongdeog (85), Dongiin (81), Daechong (84), <u>Bonggwang (74)</u>
7	Baegunchal (79), Pungsan (81), <u>Nampung (81)</u>	Chiag (81), Gwangmyeong (84), Namyang (83)
8	Saetbeol (77), Geumgang (77)	<u>Daechang (81)</u> , Yeomyeong (77), Jinheung (62), Palgeum (67). <u>Chugwang (81)</u>
9	Milyang 23 (76), Sujeong (81), <u>Yeongpung (82)</u> , Nopung (77), Tongil (71), Yushin (75), Hwanggeum (76), <u>Chilseong (84)</u>	<u>Seonam (82)</u> , <u>Giho (83)</u> , Cheonma (84), Jiniu (79), <u>Nagdong (75)</u> , Samnam (81), <u>Chucheone (70)</u>

^aTotal planting area of underlined varieties is more than 5,000 ha for Tongil type, and more than 10,000 ha for japonica type as of 1986. Figures in parentheses indicate year the variety was released.

planted in more than 10,000 ha each until 1984, but their levels of quantitative (partial or field) resistance are not known because compatible isolates were either absent or extremely low in frequency. Variety Samgang was cultivated in more than 130,000 ha from 1984 to 1987, yet no severe BI outbreak was observed. Several varieties scoring 4 or 5, such as Seomjin, Milyang 42, and Milyang 30, have high levels of quantitative resistance. They occasionally may require one or two chemical applications. Varieties that scored 6 frequently need four applications, two for leaf BI and two for

Table 2. Common features of Korean varieties in each ranking group of BI severity in farmers' fields. Korea, 1988.

Rank	Common features
1	Extremely low incidence and severity.
3	Low incidence with minor damage. Chemical application seldom necessary.
5	BI is common. Low to moderate severity, without severe yield loss. Three or fewer chemical applications sufficient.
7	Moderate to high incidence and severity. Four or five application needed.
9	Severe BI and significant yield loss. Extensive chemical application required, with control less than anticipated.